

TEACHING ENGLISH IN MEDICAL STUDENTS BY USING MODERN APPROACHES AND INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Abstract. *In teaching English as a foreign language, in the development of speech competences, it is important to use the pragmatic aspect and modern approaches and interactive methods. This article is devoted to how to improve the students' pragmatic competence by using the modern approaches and innovative methods in teaching English in medical groups and the description of methods and the issues of creating methodical support in teaching English.*

Developing exercises and tasks related to teaching English in the field of medicine developed and put into practice, organization of personalized education and transparency in education.

Key words: *innovative, knowledge, communicative competence, pragmatic aspect, understanding, interactive method.*

ОБУЧЕНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ СТУДЕНТОВ МЕДИЦИНЫ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПОДХОДОВ И ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ

Аннотация. *При обучении английскому языку как иностранному в развитии речевых компетенций важно использовать прагматический аспект и современные подходы и интерактивные методы. Данная статья посвящена вопросам повышения прагматической компетентности студентов путем использования современных подходов и инновационных методов преподавания английского языка в медицинских группах, а также описанию методов и вопросов создания методического обеспечения преподавания английского языка. Разработаны и внедрены в практику развивающие упражнения и задания, связанные с преподаванием английского языка в сфере медицины, организацией персонализированного обучения и прозрачности обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *инновационность, знания, коммуникативная компетентность, прагматический аспект, понимание, интерактивный метод.*

Introduction: Nowadays, teaching and learning foreign languages is one of the most important aim and opportunities and great attentions have been given for that in our country. On December 10, 2012, the Presidential Decree “On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages” expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. In our republic, new methods and requirements for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of European countries (CEFR, IELTS, PIRLS, and PISA). According to it, textbooks and educational materials are being created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day.

Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, age, listening comprehension and speaking), and separate concepts, skills and skills are given for each of them.

Educational technologies mean effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. Currently, the role of the modern approach in language learning and teaching is incomparable.

Literary review: A number of scholars have expressed their opinions about the use of interactive methods in the higher education system, including A. Abduqadirov, L. Golish, R. Djurayev, R. Ishmukhamedov, modern technologies are given special attention defined, J. Jalolov, N. Muslimov, M. Usmonboyeva and others studied the issues of practical application of knowledge, skills and competences acquired by pedagogical technologies, N. Azizkhodjayeva, N. Saydakhmedov, In the work of Khodzhanizayeva and others, the methods of demonstrating pedagogical skills were studied in detail. Modern methods of teaching by scientists from the countries of the Commonwe

alth of Independent States (CIS) such as K. Angelovsky, V. Beshpalko, T. Vasilyeva, V. Monakhov, Z. Slastyonin, BShadrikov scientific researches were carried out. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies by scientists such as Dewey, H. Cairns, Sure de F, H.D. Brown, Gardner, R.C and Lambert, Domyei Zolton, J. Hammond, P. Mehisto, D. Marsh, M. J Frigols, problematic the issues of education have been thoroughly studied among the foreign scientists. In our republic, there are textbooks, training manuals and a number of audio-visual materials based on different approaches to teaching a foreign language and forming their speaking competences.

Research methodology: The use of technological devices comes in handy in every aspect of foreign language learning (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking) with interactive, non-traditional tasks. For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, compliance with grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them.

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful methods, and it is advisable to use it in a combinative way with interactive tasks. In this process, including:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language video clips, demonstrations, dialogues, films or cartoons, and at the same time learn by imitating them;
- possibility to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs;
- to have a large base of language learning through the use of smartphones and social networks, which are considered non-traditional methods;

The use of this technical equipment ensures that the process of learning a foreign language is more interesting and effective for students, besides, by means of mobile games, students' attention is focused in one place during the lesson. It is known that the lesson is based on various games, which expands the opportunities of students and helps them to show their hidden abilities, concentrate, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The teaching method,

which consists of a combination of role-playing games and activities aimed at finding solutions to problem situations, prevents students from losing their attention during the lesson and creates skills in finding solutions to problems and conducting independent research.

According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of action games rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express one, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics.

Educational games should be based on educational subjects. In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely.

Today, we cannot imagine language learning and teaching without computer technologies.

At the same time, the teacher now explains all the information and does not organize a lesson in the traditional way, but only instructs and explains and creates an opportunity for students to search independently. Instead, it requires a system of unusual innovative interactive tasks and lesson organization in the educational process. When interactive tasks are used, competition, competition, argumentative spirit strongly affects the intellectual activity of students. This is manifested when people look for a solution to a problem in an organized manner. In addition, he is influenced by such psychological factors, and urges him to express his similar, close, or completely opposite opinion to any opinion expressed by those around him. Below we will consider the differences and effective aspects of interactive methods and tasks from the traditional educational process.

The role and possibilities of interactive methods and assignments in the educational and training process: Interactive method - by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process, it serves to activate the acquisition of knowledge of students and to develop their personal qualities. The use of interactive methods helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The main criteria of interactive education: conducting informal debates, the opportunity to freely describe and express the educational material, the number of lectures is small, but the number of seminars is large, the creation of opportunities for students to take initiative, small group, large group, class team assignment, written work and other methods, which are of special importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work.

Reasons for the effectiveness of interactive training: Currently, one of the main directions in the field of improving educational methods is the introduction of interactive education and training methods. Teachers of all subjects are increasingly using interactive methods in the course of lessons. As a result of the use of interactive methods, the students' skills of independent thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, expressing their opinion, being able to defend it based on reasons, healthy communication, discussion, debate are formed and developed.

In this matter, the American psychologist and pedagogue B. Bloom created taxonomy of pedagogical goals in cognitive and emotional areas, which is called B. Bloom's taxonomy (Taxonomy-a theory of classification and systematization of complex structured areas of existence). He divided thinking into six levels according to the development of cognitive abilities. According to him, the development of thinking is at the levels of knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, generalization, and evaluation. Each of these levels is represented by the following symbols and examples of verbs corresponding to each level, including: Knowing is the initial thinking level where the student can pronounce terms, know specific rules, concepts, facts,

and so on. Examples of verbs according to this level of thinking: to be able to return, to be able to strengthen, to be able to convey information, to be able to tell, to be able to write, to be able to express, to distinguish, to be able to recognize, to tell, to repeat.

When having comprehension level thinking, the student understands facts, rules, schemes, tables. Based on the available information, he can predict future consequences.

Examples of verbs according to this level of thinking: justify, replace, clarify, define, explain, translate, rearrange, illuminate, interpret, and clarify. At the level of application thinking, the student also in non-traditional situations and apply them correctly.

Examples of verbs according to this level of thinking: introduce, calculate, demonstrate, use, teach, determine, implement, calculate, implement, solve. At the analytical level of thinking, the student can distinguish parts of the whole and their interrelationships see errors in the logic of thinking, distinguish between facts and consequences, and evaluate the importance of information.

Examples of verbs according to this level of thinking: generate, separate, classify, classify, guess, predict, spread, distribute, check, group. Students perform creative work at the level of generalization, plan an experiment, and use knowledge in several areas. Examples of verbs according to this level of thinking are: to innovate, to generalize, to combine, to plan, to develop, to systematize, to combine, to create, to compose, to design. At the evaluative level of thinking, students are able to distinguish language learning criteria, follow them, see the variety of criteria, evaluate the compatibility of conclusions with available information, and distinguish between facts and evaluative opinions.

Examples of verbs according to this level of thinking are: diagnose, prove measure, control, justify, approve, evaluate, check, compare, and contrast. There are many different interactive methods, and all of them, like any progressive methods, first of all, require a lot of preparation from the teacher before the lesson.

Analysis and results: In the organization of these classes, the main features of the interactive lesson can be more clearly understood by considering some of its differences compared to the traditional lesson.

Nowadays, interactive methods are used in conducting interactive training. In the future, these methods will to some extent be combined with interactive technology. In our opinion, the difference between the concepts of this interactive method and technology can be described as follows. Interactive education method is implemented by each teacher at the level of available tools and capabilities. In this, each student learns at different levels according to his motivations and intellectual level. Interactive learning technology ensures that every teacher can provide an engaging lesson for all students.

Conclusion: Therefore, in conclusion, it can be said that secondary processing is carried out by the teacher in order to improve the design of educational materials from a didactic and methodological point of view, to apply them to the educational process, that is, the educational process is designed. It is necessary to pay special attention to increasing the student's activity in the design of educational materials. At the same time, it is desirable to implement this task with the help of interactive methods that are widely used in educational practice.

The cooperative activities of the teacher and the student (under the influence of all didactic factors) are ensured only in a fixed and defined time interval. Educational texts occupy the main

place as educational tools. At the same time, educational texts are presented in new educational tools (electronic textbooks, video films, audio lessons, audio and video cassettes, video discs and other information technologies).

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